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Mixing and indirect CP violation in two-body Charm decays at LHCb

Tommaso Pajero - Scuola Normale Superiore & INFN, Pisa
on behalf of the LHCb collaboration

Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare

SCUOLA
NORMALE
SUPERIORE

tommaso.pajero@gmail.com

Overview

1) A_{Γ} with Run 1 prompt data (3 fb⁻¹)

[\[PRL 118, 261803 \(2017\)\]](#)

2) **Mixing and CP violation in $D^0 \rightarrow K^{\pm}\pi^{\mp}$ decays**
with 2011–2016 prompt data (5 fb⁻¹)

[\[PRD 97, 031101 \(2018\)\]](#)

3) y_{CP} with Run 1 semileptonic-tagged data (3 fb⁻¹)

[\[PRL 122, 011802 \(2018\)\]](#)

Mixing and CPV in charm

Mixing is established.

- Mixing parameters: $x = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{\Gamma}$ $y = \frac{\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1}{2\Gamma}$ $\Gamma = \frac{\Gamma_1 + \Gamma_2}{2}$
- Mass eigenstates: $|D_{1,2}\rangle = p|D^0\rangle \pm q|\bar{D}^0\rangle$

[Eur. Phys. J. C77 \(2017\) 895](https://arxiv.org/abs/1708.07401)
<https://hflav.web.cern.ch>

CPV still not observed.

- Charm is the only up-type quark where CPV can be fully investigated;
- CPV $< \mathcal{O}(10^{-3})$ in the SM, BSM contributions could enhance it.

A_{Γ} with Run 1 data

A_Γ definition

- Measure of indirect CPV in D^0 singly-Cabibbo-suppressed decays to CP eigenstates:

$$A_{\text{CP}}(t) = \frac{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow f) - \Gamma(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow f)}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow f) + \Gamma(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow f)} \approx A_{\text{CP}}^{\text{dir}} - A_\Gamma \left(\frac{t}{\tau} \right), \quad f = K^+K^-, \pi^+\pi^-$$

$$A_\Gamma = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) y \cos \phi + \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| + \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) x \sin \phi \right] \approx y \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - 1 \right) - x \phi$$

$$\text{with } \phi = \arg \left(-\frac{q}{p} \frac{\bar{A}_f}{A_f} \right)$$

- If $A_\Gamma \neq 0 \rightarrow$ indirect CPV.

[\[PRL 118, 261803 \(2017\)\]](#)

- At LHCb: measurement performed with Run 1 data (3 fb^{-1})
- D^0 flavour from strong decay $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0 \pi_s^+$ (prompt).

Data sample

$$\Delta m = m(h^+ h^- \pi_S^\pm) - m(h^+ h^-)$$

- Cuts on $m(h^+h^-)$, PID, IP of D^0 daughters.

Detection charge asymmetries

CP-symmetric,
no asymmetries

large detection
asymmetries

- Trigger introduces correlations between the measured decay time of the D^0 and the momentum of the π_s^+ ;
- momentum-dependent detection asymmetries reflect in time-dependent asymmetries mimicking a fake A_Γ value as large as 10^{-3} ($3\sigma(A_\Gamma)$).
- Reweigh the 3D momentum distribution of the π_s^- to match that of π_s^+ .
- Validated on $D^0 \rightarrow K \pi^+$ (no CPV expected).

[PRL 118, 261803 (2017)]

Charge asymmetry of the π_s

$$k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{p_x^2 + p_z^2}}, \quad \theta_x = \arctan\left(\frac{p_x}{p_z}\right)$$

Secondary decays

- Measured decay-time of D^0 from b -hadrons biased to higher values \rightarrow their fraction increases as a function of time;
- B production asymmetry different from D^{*+} ;
- secondary decays induce time-dependent asymmetries.

- Suppressed requiring the D^0 to come from the PV ($\chi^2_{IP} < 9$);
- residual fraction estimated through a model whose normalization is fixed using the yields at high decay times.

χ^2_{IP} = difference in pp vertex-fit χ^2 reconstructed with and without the particle

[PRL 118, 261803 (2017)]

Results

[PRL 118, 261803 (2017)]

$$A_{\Gamma}^{KK} = (-3.0 \pm 3.2 \pm 1.0) \cdot 10^{-4}$$

$$A_{\Gamma}^{\pi\pi} = (4.6 \pm 5.8 \pm 1.2) \cdot 10^{-4}$$

- Sys. unc. dominated by secondary decays and multi-body partially and misreconstructed D-meson decays.

- Combination with the smaller, independent muon-tagged sample $\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \mu^- X$ [JHEP 04 (2015) 043]:

$$A_{\Gamma} = (-2.9 \pm 2.8) \cdot 10^{-4}$$

- dominates the world average
- compatible with zero within $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Mixing and CPV with $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$ decays

Mixing in $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$

- Wrong sign (WS) decays:

a time-dependent WS decay rate implies mixing

- Right sign (RS) decays:

decay rate nearly independent of time

Assuming negligible CPV:

$$R(t) = \frac{\Gamma_{\text{WS}}(t)}{\Gamma_{\text{RS}}(t)} = \underbrace{R_D}_{\text{DCS decay}} + \underbrace{\sqrt{R_D} y' \left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right)}_{\text{interference}} + \underbrace{\frac{(x')^2 + (y')^2}{4} \left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right)^2}_{\text{mixing + CF decay}}$$

$$x' = x \cos \delta + y \sin \delta$$

$$y' = y \cos \delta - x \sin \delta$$

$$\frac{A(D^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-)}{A(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-)} = -\sqrt{R_D} e^{-i\delta}$$

CP violation in $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$

- Measure WS/RS(t) separately for D^{*+} and D^{*-} decays:

$$R^\pm(t) = \frac{\Gamma_{WS}^\pm(t)}{\Gamma_{RS}^\pm(t)} = R_D^\pm + \sqrt{R_D^\pm} y^\pm \left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right) + \frac{(x^\pm)^2 + (y^\pm)^2}{4} \left(\frac{t}{\tau}\right)^2$$

direct CPV
 $R_D^+ \neq R_D^-$

CPV in the mixing or interference

$$x^\pm = \left| \frac{q}{p} \right|^{\pm 1} [x \cos(\delta \pm \phi) + y \sin(\delta \pm \phi)]$$

$$y^\pm = \left| \frac{q}{p} \right|^{\pm 1} [y \cos(\delta \pm \phi) - x \sin(\delta \pm \phi)]$$

$\phi = \arg(q/p)$

- D^{*+} production cross section and π^+_S detection asymmetry cancel out in the ratio; need to account only for **$K\pi$ detection asymmetry**:

$$\frac{N_{WS}^\pm}{N_{RS}^\pm} = \frac{N(D^{*\pm} \rightarrow [K^\pm \pi^\mp]_{D^0} \pi_S^\pm)}{N(D^{*\pm} \rightarrow [K^\mp \pi^\pm]_{D^0} \pi_S^\pm)} = R^\pm \frac{\epsilon(K^\pm \pi^\mp)}{\epsilon(K^\mp \pi^\pm)}$$

Data sample

- 5 fb⁻¹ (2011–2016);
- prompt decays, sample selection ≈ that of A_Γ.
- **A(K⁻π⁺)** accounted for employing measured asymmetries of $D^+ \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \pi^+$ and $D^+ \rightarrow \bar{K}^0 \pi^+$ decays, reweighed to make their kinematic distributions coincide with that of $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$

estimated at LHCb
in [\[JHEP 07 \(2013\) 041\]](#)

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_D(K^- \pi^+) &= A_{\text{raw}}(K^- \pi^+ \pi^+) - A_{\text{raw}}(\bar{K}^0 \pi^+) + A_D(\bar{K}^0) \\
 &= \cancel{A_D(D^+)} + A_D(K^- \pi^+) + \cancel{A_D(\pi^+)} \\
 &\quad - \cancel{A_D(D^+)} - \cancel{A_D(\bar{K}^0)} - \cancel{A_D(\pi^+)} \\
 &\quad + \cancel{A_D(\bar{K}^0)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Ghost tagging π_s^+

- It may happen that clusters belonging to the π_s track in the tracking stations upstream the magnet are matched to wrong clusters downstream it;
 - measured direction between D^0 and π_s is correct \rightarrow bkg. peaks in $m(D^{*+})$ even if reconstructed $p(\pi_s)$ is wrong;
 - RS decay is tagged as much rarer WS \approx half of the times.

- Misreconstruction probability must be kept well under $BR(D^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-) / BR(D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+) \approx 3 \times 10^{-3}$
 - neural-network-based algorithm (occupancies & hit multiplicities in each subdetector, momentum of the track) [\[LHCb-PUB-2017-011\]](#)
 - accounts for 30—50% of sys. uncertainty.

Results

- No evidence for CPV

- If no CPV is assumed:

$$x^2 = (0.039 \pm 0.023 \pm 0.014) \cdot 10^{-3}$$

$$y' = (5.28 \pm 0.45 \pm 0.27) \cdot 10^{-3}$$

- Twice as precise as previous superseded LHCb measurement [PRL 111 251801 (2013)]

γ_{CP} with $\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \mu^- X$ tagging

y_{CP} definition

$$y_{\text{CP}} = \frac{\hat{\Gamma}(D^0 \rightarrow h^+h^-) + \hat{\Gamma}(\bar{D}^0 \rightarrow h^+h^-)}{2\Gamma} - 1$$

$$f = K^+K^-, \pi^+\pi^- \quad (\text{CP-even})$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| + \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) y \cos \phi - \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - \left| \frac{p}{q} \right| \right) x \sin \phi \right] \approx y + y \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - 1 \right)^2 - \frac{\phi^2}{2} \right] - x\phi \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - 1 \right)$$

- equal to y in the limit of no CPV;
 - differences are
 - linear in mixing parameters
 - quadratic in ϕ , $|q/p|-1$
- } 5% of y or less
- current precision ($\approx 20\%$) not as competitive as A_{F} for CPV searches;
 - it is a measurement of y independent of $R(t) = WS/RS$.
 - First measurement at LHCb [\[JHEP 04 \(2012\) 129\]](#) with prompt decays but very limited data sample (2010, 29 pb⁻¹), not competitive with world average.

New LHCb measurement

- 3 fb⁻¹ (Run 1);
- tagging with $\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \mu^- X$
- lower yield w.r.t. prompt decays;
- hardware and first level software trigger on the muon;
 - smaller trigger-induced decay-time biases.
- Extract y_{CP} from the time-dependent ratio between h^+h^- and $K\pi^+$ yields (same strategy as B_s, D_s lifetimes measurements at LHCb [\[PRL 119, 101801\]](#)).

$\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \mu^- X$ selection

- Mainly inherited from muon-tagged ΔA_{CP} and B_s , D_s lifetimes measurements
[\[JHEP 07 \(2014\) 041\]](#), [\[PRL 119, 101801\]](#)
- loose cuts on all tracks χ^2_{IP} ;
- cut in the $p_T(D^0) - m_{corr}(B)$ plane to reduce contamination from combinatorial bkg., double-charmed B decays,
 $\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \tau^- X$
- Final contamination in $m(D^0)$ peak:
 - < 1.5% from these bkg.
 - < 1% from prompt D^0 .

$$m_{corr}(B) = \sqrt{m^2(D\mu) + p_{\perp}^2(D\mu) + p_{\perp}^2(D\mu)}$$

χ^2_{IP} = difference in pp vertex-fit χ^2
 reconstructed with and without the particle

Experimental strategy

- Inspired by [\[PRL 119, 101801\]](#):
 - determine the yields of h^+h^- and $K\pi^+$ through a fit to $m(D^0)$, separately for 19 bins of decay time;
 - minimise the χ^2 from the difference of $N_i(h^+h^-) / N_i(K\pi^+)$ with the expected value:

$$R_i = N \cdot A_i \cdot \frac{\int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} e^{-(\Gamma + \Delta_\Gamma)t} dt}{\int_{t_i}^{t_{i+1}} e^{-\Gamma t} dt}$$

normalisation factor
common to all time bins

acceptance ratio in time bin i
(from MC)

ratio of the PDFs of h^+h^- and $K\pi^+$ decays
(nearly independent of the value of Γ)

$$\Delta_\Gamma = \Gamma_{h^+h^-} - \Gamma$$
$$y_{\text{CP}} = \frac{\Delta_\Gamma}{\Gamma}$$

Acceptance ratio

- Acceptances calculated from MC simulation of inclusive B^0 , B^- semi-muonic decays into D^0 ;
- main MC mismodellings of detector *etc.* expected to cancel in the ratio.

Null test (1): $\frac{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+), \chi^2_{\text{IP}} > 60}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+), \chi^2_{\text{IP}} > 8}$

- Test the MC description of the time-dependence of the acceptance:
 - split the $K\pi^+$ sample in two;
 - apply a tighter cut $\chi^2_{\text{IP}} > 60$ to the μ^-, K^-, π^+ of the numerator sample (std. is $\chi^2_{\text{IP}} > 8$);
 - measure Δ_Γ between the two samples (should be 0).

[PRL 122, 011802 (2018)]

nearly 30% variations
of acceptance ratio

$$\Delta_\Gamma^{K\pi/K\pi} = (-1.8 \pm 3.3) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ ps}^{-1}$$

uncertainty corresponds to
 $\sigma(y_{\text{CP}}) = 0.14 \%$

Null test (2): $\frac{\Gamma(D^+ \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \pi^+)}{\Gamma(D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+)}$

- 3-body vs. 2-body decays \rightarrow different topology, kinematics, acceptance;
- (B^0 : B^-) very different for D^0 and D^+ \rightarrow check impact of B-mixture uncertainty in MC;
- $\tau(D^+) / \tau(D^0) \approx 2.5$ \rightarrow sensitive to biases linear in Δ_Γ .

[PRL 122, 011802 (2018)]

$\tau(D^+) / \tau(D^0) = 2.5141 \pm 0.0082$
 compatible with PDG within 1σ
 (test limited by PDG precision
 2.536 ± 0.019).

Biases linear in Δ_Γ are $< 0.8\% \Delta_\Gamma$.

Other checks and systematics

[\[PRL 122, 011802 \(2018\)\]](#)

- Further checks:

- $\frac{\Gamma(D^+ \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \pi^+), \chi^2_{\text{IP}} > 60}{\Gamma(D^+ \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \pi^+), \chi^2_{\text{IP}} > 8}$
- $\frac{\Gamma(D^+ \rightarrow K^- K^+ \pi^+)}{\Gamma(D^+ \rightarrow K^- \pi^+ \pi^+)}$

} Δ_Γ consistent with 0
within stat. uncertainty

- Systematic uncertainties:

Source	KK (%)	$\pi\pi$ (%)	
Finite size of MC sample (acceptance ratio)	0.11	0.15	} uncorrelated
Fit bias	0.02	0.02	
B^0 : B^- ratio and decay model	0.02	0.02	} fully correlated
Decay-time resolution	0.01	0.01	
B - B bar production asymm.	< 0.01	< 0.01	
Total sys.	0.11	0.15	
Statistical	0.15	0.28	

Fit result

[PRL 122, 011802 (2018)]

$$y_{\text{CP}}^{KK} = (0.63 \pm 0.15 \pm 0.11) \%$$

$$y_{\text{CP}}^{\pi\pi} = (0.38 \pm 0.28 \pm 0.15) \%$$

$$y_{\text{CP}} = (0.57 \pm 0.13 \pm 0.09) \%$$

- Compatible and with same precision of world average $(0.835 \pm 0.155) \%$;
- compatible with $y = \left(0.67^{+0.06}_{-0.13}\right) \%$ within 1σ .

Summary

- LHCb leads the world averages of all indirect CPV parameters thanks to huge $c\text{-}\bar{c}$ prompt production at LHC;
 - now eventually entering the region allowed by the SM, $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})$;
- uncertainty on mixing parameters steadily decreasing, other 4 fb^{-1} of data taken in 2017—2018;
- analyses still limited by the statistical uncertainty.

Thank you for your attention.
Any questions?

Backup

A_Γ : systematics

[\[PRL 118, 261803 \(2017\)\]](#)

Source	KK (10^{-4})	$\pi\pi$ (10^{-4})
Secondary decays	0.8	1.2
Discretisation of weighing procedure	0.2	0.2
Subtraction of Δm bkg. from random π^+_s	0.1	0.1
Bkg. from partially-reconstructed and misidentified D-meson multi-body decays	0.5	-
Total sys.	1.0	1.2
Statistical	3.2	5.8

A_{Γ} : contribution from secondary decays

$$A_{\text{raw}} = A_{\text{prim}}(t) + f_{\text{sec}}(t) \cdot [A_{\text{sec}}(t) - A_{\text{prim}}(t)]$$

[PRL 118, 261803 (2017)]

$$\approx A_{\text{production}}(B) - A_{\text{production}}(D^{*+})$$

f_{sec} extracted from $\ln(\chi_{\text{IP}}^2)$ fit in last four time bins and extrapolated with physically-motivated empiric model to lower bins where the distributions of prompt and secondary decays can't be easily disentangled. Uncertainty on the empiric model is the main source of systematic uncertainty.

A_Γ and y_{CP} world averages

[Eur. Phys. J. C77 \(2017\) 895](https://hflav.web.cern.ch)
<https://hflav.web.cern.ch>

Indirect CPV: $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$ vs A_Γ

$D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$: determines the 8-like shape of allowed $(\phi, |q/p|)$ region; nearly full degeneracy $\phi \rightarrow -\phi$

[Eur. Phys. J. C77 \(2017\) 895](https://arxiv.org/abs/1708.07584)
<https://hflav.web.cern.ch>

[PRD 97, 031101 \(2018\)](https://arxiv.org/abs/1801.03110)

$$A_\Gamma \approx y \left(\left| \frac{q}{p} \right| - 1 \right) - x\phi$$

- it's a line in the plane
- responsible for the tilt (and significant reduction of CPV-allowed region w.r.t. $D^0 \rightarrow K^\pm \pi^\mp$ constraints only)

Tagging strategies at LHCb

To identify the flavour at production of the D^0 meson:

- **Prompt tag:** strong decay $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0 \pi_S^+$
 - larger production cross section;
 - tight trigger cut on D^0 flight distance and h^+ , h^- impact parameters to improve S/B;
 - low trigger efficiency at low decay times;
 - D^0 points at the primary vertex (PV).
- **Semileptonic tag:** weak decay $\bar{B} \rightarrow D^0 \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu X$
 - lower production cross section;
 - no need to cut on D^0 flight distance;
 - all D^0 decay times collected by the trigger;
 - total yield $\approx 25\%$ of prompt one;
 - D^0 does not necessarily point at PV.
- **Double-tag:** $\bar{B} \rightarrow [D^0 \pi_S^+]_{D^{*+}} \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu X$
 - highest purity;
 - lowest yield.

Indirect CPV prospects at LHCb Upgrade II

Sample (\mathcal{L})	Yield ($\times 10^6$)	$\sigma(x_{K\pi}^{\prime 2})$	$\sigma(y'_{K\pi})$	$\sigma(A_D)$	$\sigma(q/p)$	$\sigma(\phi)$
Run 1–2 (9 fb^{-1})	1.8	1.5×10^{-5}	2.9×10^{-4}	0.51%	0.12	10°
Run 1–3 (23 fb^{-1})	10	6.4×10^{-6}	1.2×10^{-4}	0.22%	0.05	4°
Run 1–4 (50 fb^{-1})	25	3.9×10^{-6}	7.6×10^{-5}	0.14%	0.03	3°
Run 1–5 (300 fb^{-1})	170	1.5×10^{-6}	2.9×10^{-5}	0.05%	0.01	1°

Sample (\mathcal{L})	Tag	Yield K^+K^-	$\sigma(A_\Gamma)$	Yield $\pi^+\pi^-$	$\sigma(A_\Gamma)$
Run 1–2 (9 fb^{-1})	Prompt	60M	0.013%	18M	0.024%
Run 1–3 (23 fb^{-1})	Prompt	310M	0.0056%	92M	0.0104 %
Run 1–4 (50 fb^{-1})	Prompt	793M	0.0035%	236M	0.0065 %
Run 1–5 (300 fb^{-1})	Prompt	5.3G	0.0014%	1.6G	0.0025 %

[Physics case for an LHCb Upgrade II \[arXiv:1808.08865\]](#)

Assumptions:

- x2 of hadron trigger efficiency (no hardware trigger + new magnet stations);
- current LHCb performance is maintained in Upgrade II conditions;
- statistical uncertainty only (with $1/\sqrt{N}$ scaling).

|q/p|

LHCb detector

The LHCb detector at the LHC, JINST 3 S08005 (2008)